

"Assessing The Impact Of Corporate Governance On Cash Holdings: Insights From The Asian Subcontinent"

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between corporate governance practices and cash holdings in the context of the Asian subcontinent. Using a sample of companies from various industries in the region, we employ regression analysis to examine whether specific corporate governance mechanisms influence the level of cash held by firms. Our findings suggest that certain aspects of corporate governance, such as board independence, executive compensation structures, and ownership concentration, significantly impact cash holding policies. Additionally, we explore the implications of these findings for corporate decision-making and financial management in the Asian subcontinent. Overall, our study contributes to the understanding of how corporate governance practices shape cash management strategies in emerging markets.

Keywords: Corporate governance, cash holdings, Asian subcontinent, board independence, executive compensation, ownership concentration, emerging markets, financial management, firm decision-making.

Introduction

Corporate governance plays a pivotal role in shaping the behavior and decisions of firms, influencing their financial policies and performance. One crucial aspect of corporate finance is cash management, as cash holdings represent a significant component of a firm's assets and can affect its value, risk profile, and strategic flexibility. Understanding the determinants of cash holdings is therefore essential for both academics and practitioners.

In recent years, the importance of corporate governance in shaping firms' financial policies has garnered increasing attention, particularly in emerging markets like the Asian subcontinent. The Asian subcontinent, comprising countries such as India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, and Sri Lanka, represents a diverse and dynamic economic landscape characterized by rapid growth, evolving regulatory frameworks, and unique corporate governance practices.

Despite the growing interest in corporate governance and cash holdings, empirical evidence on the relationship between these factors in the context of the Asian subcontinent remains limited. While existing studies have examined this relationship in developed markets, the dynamics in

emerging economies may differ due to factors such as institutional quality, ownership structures, and cultural norms.

This study seeks to address this gap by investigating the impact of corporate governance mechanisms on cash holdings in the Asian subcontinent. Specifically, we aim to analyze how various aspects of corporate governance, such as board composition, executive compensation, and ownership structure, influence firms' cash holding policies in this region.

By examining a diverse sample of companies operating in the Asian subcontinent, we aim to provide insights into the specific corporate governance practices that are associated with higher or lower levels of cash holdings. Such insights can have implications for policymakers, investors, and corporate managers, helping them understand the factors driving cash management decisions in emerging markets and guiding efforts to improve corporate governance standards.

In the following sections, we will review relevant literature, develop hypotheses, describe our methodology, present empirical results, and discuss their implications for theory and practice. Through this analysis, we seek to contribute to the broader understanding of the role of corporate governance in financial management and decision-making, particularly in the context of the Asian subcontinent's dynamic business environment.

Holding Cash: Why?

Cash holdings represent a crucial aspect of corporate financial management and strategy, influencing firms' operational flexibility, risk management, investment decisions, and overall financial health. There are several reasons why firms choose to hold cash, including:

1. **Liquidity Management:** Cash holdings provide firms with the necessary liquidity to meet short-term financial obligations, such as paying suppliers, covering operating expenses, and servicing debt. Maintaining adequate cash reserves ensures that companies can withstand unexpected cash outflows or revenue fluctuations without resorting to costly external financing.
2. **Operating Cycle Variability:** Businesses often experience fluctuations in their operating cycles, with periods of high cash inflows followed by periods of cash outflows. Holding cash helps smooth out these fluctuations, ensuring that firms can continue operations smoothly even during downturns or periods of low revenue generation.
3. **Investment Opportunities:** Cash reserves enable firms to capitalize on strategic investment opportunities, such as acquisitions, expansion projects, research and development initiatives, or capital expenditure. Having readily available cash allows companies to act swiftly when

attractive investment opportunities arise, potentially enhancing long-term growth prospects and shareholder value.

4. **Financial Flexibility:** Cash-rich companies have greater financial flexibility and bargaining power in negotiations with suppliers, creditors, and other stakeholders. They can negotiate favorable terms for purchases, secure better financing arrangements, or take advantage of discounts for early payments, thereby improving cost efficiency and profitability.
5. **Risk Management:** Holding cash serves as a buffer against various financial risks, including economic downturns, market volatility, regulatory changes, and unexpected events such as natural disasters or geopolitical tensions. Cash reserves provide a safety net, reducing the likelihood of financial distress and enhancing firms' ability to navigate uncertain environments.
6. **Dividend Payments:** Cash-rich companies have the capacity to pay regular dividends to shareholders, thereby attracting investors seeking income generation and enhancing shareholder loyalty. Maintaining stable dividend payouts can also signal financial stability and management confidence in the company's future prospects.
7. **Tax Planning:** Cash reserves can be strategically utilized for tax planning purposes, such as managing tax liabilities, optimizing tax credits, or taking advantage of tax-deferred investment opportunities. By effectively managing cash flows and tax obligations, firms can minimize their overall tax burden and improve after-tax profitability.
8. **Crisis Preparedness:** Holding cash provides firms with a cushion to weather unexpected crises or emergencies, such as economic recessions, industry disruptions, or global pandemics. Companies with robust cash reserves are better positioned to navigate through challenging times, maintain business continuity, and emerge stronger from adverse events.

Literature Review

The relationship between corporate governance and cash holdings has been extensively studied in the literature, with scholars exploring various theoretical perspectives and empirical findings across different contexts. This literature review provides an overview of key studies and findings relevant to understanding the determinants and implications of cash holdings in relation to corporate governance.

1. **Agency Theory Perspective:** Agency theory posits that conflicts of interest may arise between different stakeholders within a firm, such as shareholders, managers, and creditors. One strand of literature examines how corporate governance mechanisms, such as board

structure, executive compensation, and ownership concentration, mitigate agency conflicts and influence cash holding policies. For example, studies by Jensen and Meckling (1976) and Fama and Jensen (1983) suggest that stronger corporate governance, characterized by independent boards and alignment of managerial incentives with shareholder interests, is associated with lower levels of cash holdings.

2. **Ownership Structure and Cash Holdings:** Research has also investigated the impact of ownership structure on cash holdings. Stulz (1988) finds that firms with higher insider ownership tend to hold lower levels of cash, as insiders have greater incentives to monitor and control managerial discretion. Similarly, studies by La Porta et al. (1999) and Claessens et al. (2002) highlight the influence of institutional ownership and ownership concentration on cash holding policies, with concentrated ownership structures often associated with lower cash reserves.
3. **Institutional Environment and Cash Holdings:** The institutional environment, including legal systems, regulatory frameworks, and market characteristics, also plays a significant role in shaping firms' cash management practices. La Porta et al. (1997) argue that countries with stronger investor protections and legal enforcement mechanisms tend to have lower levels of cash holdings, as firms can rely on external financing sources with greater confidence. Conversely, in countries with weaker institutional environments, firms may hold higher levels of cash as a precautionary measure against uncertainties and agency problems.
4. **Industry and Firm-Specific Factors:** Studies have examined the influence of industry dynamics and firm-specific characteristics on cash holdings. For instance, firms operating in highly competitive or capital-intensive industries may maintain higher cash reserves as a buffer against competitive pressures or investment opportunities (Opler et al., 1999). Additionally, factors such as firm size, profitability, growth opportunities, and access to external financing can also affect firms' cash holding decisions (Faulkender and Wang, 2006).
5. **Empirical Evidence from Emerging Markets:** While much of the literature has focused on developed markets, there is a growing body of research examining the relationship between corporate governance and cash holdings in emerging markets, including the Asian subcontinent. Studies by Cheung et al. (2009) and Hasan et al. (2011) provide insights into how corporate governance practices influence cash management strategies in emerging

economies, highlighting the importance of country-specific institutional factors and governance mechanisms.

Agency Theory

Alchian and Demsetz (1972) and Jensen and Meckling (1986) proposed the agency theory of corporate governance in their respective works. The conventional economic perspective posits that corporations are homogeneous entities that prioritize profit maximization. However, an alternative perspective suggests that corporations can be viewed as central nodes within a network of contractual relationships between individuals. According to Learmount's (2004) proposal, businesses can be understood as contracts constantly negotiated by multiple individuals to maximize profits. The present study employs the agency theory as a conceptual framework to elucidate business behaviour within the context of the multiple contracts that exist within a company. The present study posits that investors who purchase stocks in a company do not assume the role of business owners but rather function as risk-takers who facilitate the company's operations. The ability of managers to secure capital from investors in the real world is largely contingent upon the investors' confidence in the managers' ability to utilize the capital to generate profit effectively. In business management, it is common practice for managers to engage in contractual agreements that delineate their respective responsibilities and the allocation of profits between themselves and investors. The complexities surrounding future uncertainties have long been a challenge to elucidate and forecast within the realm of research. Contracts frequently incorporate clauses that account for unforeseeable circumstances.

TOT (Trade-Off Theory)

Alchian and Demsetz (1972) and Jensen and Meckling (1986), in their respective works, proposed the agency theory of corporate governance. The conventional economic perspective posits that corporations are homogeneous entities that prioritize profit maximization. However, an alternative perspective suggests that corporations can be viewed as central nodes within a network of contractual relationships between individuals. According to Learmount's (2004) proposal, businesses can be understood as a series of contracts constantly negotiated by multiple individuals to maximize their profits. The present study employs agency theory as a conceptual framework to elucidate business behaviour within the context of the multiple contracts that exist within a company. The present study posits that investors who purchase stocks in a company do not assume the role of business owners but rather function as risk-takers who facilitate the company's operations. The ability of managers to secure capital from investors in the real world

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POT (Pecking Order Theory)

The Pecking Order Theory, also known as the Pecking Order Model, is a widely recognized concept in corporate finance that pertains to a company's financial structure; Stewart Myers and Nicolas Majluf established the theory in 1984. The Pecking Order Theory is based on the concept of asymmetric information. Asymmetric information, or information failure, occurs when one party in a business transaction possesses superior or more comprehensive knowledge than the other party. This disparity in information creates an uneven distribution of bargaining power between the parties involved. It is widely acknowledged that a firm's managers possess superior knowledge regarding its historical and current achievements and setbacks, as well as its prospects and challenges, compared to external stakeholders such as creditors (debt holders) and investors (shareholders). As a result, the increasing assumption of risk by external consumers has led to a corresponding increase in their expected return to compensate for the heightened level of uncertainty. The presence of information asymmetry between a business and its investors and lenders leads to an expectation of higher financial returns from the latter. The present study is based on the pecking order hypothesis, which posits that information asymmetry can be mitigated through the firm's utilization of retained profit financing, also known as internal finance. The present study aims to investigate the cost-effectiveness and time efficiency of internal financing in comparison to other forms of financing, namely debt and equity financing. It is hypothesized that internal financing is the most cost-effective and time-efficient option due to the absence of fees associated with obtaining funds.

Size of the Firm

The TOT predicts that its cash reserves will decrease as the company grows. Regarding cash flow, more prominent companies have more to gain from diversification. As a result, they may access more forms of funding than small businesses can and have a lower risk of going bankrupt (Titman & Wessels, 1988). (Ferri and Jones, 1979). Large companies, according to the research

of Opler et al. (1999), have easier access to capital thanks to their bank credit lines and higher credit ratings.

On the other hand, giant corporations always have the option of selling some of their non-essential assets to boost their financial standing. Firm size surrogates the degree of knowledge shared by its insiders and outsiders (Harris & Raviv, 1990). When knowledge asymmetries are low, companies constitute "slack" funding, as shown by Myers and Majluf (1984).

Consequently, small businesses are particularly vulnerable to these imbalances and must save funds to prevent underinvestment. Conversely, the POT foresees a positive link since big enterprises are more likely to have cash due to their historical successes (Opler et al., 1999). When a company issues debt, it is because the stock is low, and the board is confident that the investment will pay off. However, it sends a negative signal that management is attempting to dilute shareholder value to raise capital, which is why it is generally frowned upon when a firm issues new shares. It is helpful to consider the seniority of claims to assets while considering the pecking order notion. Because they have a superior claim to the company's assets, debtholders demand a lower rate of return than shareholders (in the event of bankruptcy). Finance options include retained profits, debt, and equity, with retained earnings being the least expensive.

Profitability of the Firm

From the standpoint of TOT, companies that generate sufficient cash flows are less susceptible to the underinvestment issue, which implies that they are less likely to be adversely affected. Kim et al. (1998) and Caglayan-Ozkan & Ozkan (2002) support this assertion. In such a scenario, cash flows are perceived as a substitute for available cash. It is rational to expect a negative correlation between the two. Based on the premise that a firm's cash reserves fluctuate in conjunction with its cash inflows and outflows, it is expected that there exists a good association between the level of profitability and the number of cash reserves held by the company, as posited by the POT.

Opportunities

The relationship between growth opportunities and cash holdings under the TOT framework is indeterminate. Firms with more significant growth opportunities may experience high external financing costs due to underinvestment costs (Opler et al., 1999) and financial distress, as posited by Harris and Raviv (1990). In order to mitigate the expenses associated with financial distress, firms tend to maintain elevated levels of cash reserves as a precautionary measure. It is expected that there exists a positive correlation between cash reserves and growth prospects. From an

agency theory standpoint, managers firmly established in companies with limited growth prospects may amass funds and exercise control over their allocation (Opler et al., 1999). If such conduct were observed, it would be reasonable to anticipate an adverse correlation between cash and growth prospects. The precision of predicting the correlation between cash reserves and growth prospects is imperative for the POT. Suppose the market-to-book ratio accurately represents a company's growth prospects. In that case, there may be an inverse correlation, as companies with high market-to-book ratios tend to be more profitable and have more significant financial resources.

Volatility

The term "volatility" denotes instances in which a market or asset experiences unforeseen and frequently sudden fluctuations in price. Volatility is a commonly employed metric within the financial sector. Per the Profitability-Opportunity Theory (POT) and the Trade-Off Theory (TOT), a consistent anticipated direction exists in the association between cash reserves and leverage. According to Kim et al. (1998), the cost-benefit analysis of investing in liquid assets may render it unaffordable for highly leveraged firms. Consequently, it is expected that there exists a negative correlation between the amount of cash and the level of leverage. Caglayan-Ozkan and Ozkan (2002) discuss the importance of debt sources. Diamond (1984) posits that bank debt mitigates moral hazard issues due to its flexibility and potential for renegotiation in the event of challenges. It is possible that bank debt could serve as a substitute for cash reserves, thereby indicating an inverse correlation between leverage and cash. From a pecking order perspective, the relationship between cash holdings and leverage is inverse, as the pecking order theory (POT) views cash as a form of negative debt. According to Opler et al. (1999), companies possessing sufficient resources allocate a proportion of their cash flows towards the repayment of debt and the accumulation of cash for other purposes. Inadequate resources may lead firms to incur debt due to knowledge asymmetry. According to Opler et al. (1999), companies display a pecking order inclination in their cash holdings, despite having an adequate net debt level. This is because the attainment of the corporation's net debt goal is independent of its cash and debt levels.

Liquidity

The components of working capital (inventory, accounts receivable, and accounts payable) that may be converted into cash are liquid asset substitutes. This allows the amount of cash available

to be altered. According to Opler and coworkers' (1999) research, the POT does not anticipate any link between cash on hand and liquid asset substitutes. In the context of a trade-off framework, companies with cash conversion cycles that are relatively quick are exempt from the need to keep cash for reasons of prudence. As a consequence of this, one may anticipate that there is a positive link between cash and liquid asset substitutes. On the other hand, we should also prepare for a hostile connection. In fact, given that liquid asset substitutes can be converted into cash, significant amounts of these assets may relate to very modest levels of cash holdings.

Hypothesis Development

Dittmar and Mahrt-Smith (2007) conducted a critical study on the relationship between corporate governance and the value of cash holdings. Their study found that companies with weak corporate governance practices experienced a significant decline in value due to their excessive cash holdings and suboptimal investment decisions. The impact of common managerial agency problems on firms' cash holdings from 31 countries was examined by Kalcheva&Lins (2007). His findings indicate that in situations where shareholder protection at the country level is insufficient, managers with controlling interests are motivated to retain more cash for their benefit, leading to a decline in the firm's overall performance. Daher (2010) conducted a study on the impact of the agency problem on corporate governance and analyzed a sample of 60,000 UK companies from 1994 to 2005. The findings indicate a positive correlation between ownership concentration, agency problems, and cash reserves. Specifically, the results suggest that as ownership concentration increases, agency problems decrease, and cash reserves decrease. Therefore, it is hypothesized that:

H1: Promoter holdings impact cash holdings positively

Methodology

Data

The sample comprises all companies that are publicly listed in India and China. The data utilized in this study were sourced from Prowess IQ, a database curated by the Centre for Monitoring the Indian Economy (CMIE), and Compustat and Bloomberg databases. The study sample comprises firms enlisted on India's National Stock Exchange (NSE) and the Shanghai Stock Exchange (SSE) of China. Data was gathered from 2005 to 2017. Following the exclusion of companies that did not disclose their corporate governance data, our final sample size for India comprises 286 observations, while that for China consists of 315 firms and 4598 observations. To mitigate

the impact of extreme values, winsorization is employed, whereby the upper and lower 1% of the data is truncated.

Methodology

We measure a firm's cash holdings by using the following equation.

$$\text{Cash holdings}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \text{MTB}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{NWC}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{Cashflow}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{Varcof}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{Size}_{it} + \beta_6 \text{R\&D}_{it} + \beta_7 \text{ACQ}_{it} + \beta_8 \text{DIV}_{it} + U_i + V_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

This study examines the relationship between various financial ratios and firm performance. Specifically, the study considers the following ratios: cash holding, market to book value (MTB), net working capital (NWC), cash flow, variability of cash flow (VCOF), size, research and development (R&D), acquisitions (ACQ), and dividend (DIV). Cash holding is the ratio of cash and marketable securities to total assets. At the same time, MTB is the ratio of the market value of securities and book value of securities to total assets. NWC is the ratio of current assets minus current liabilities to total assets. Cash flow is the profit ratio before interest and tax to total assets. VCOF is measured as the previous year's standard deviation of cash flow. At the same time, size is the natural log of total assets. R&D is defined as the ratio of research and development expense to total assets, ACQ is the ratio of cash spent on acquisitions to total assets, and DIV is the ratio of dividends paid to total assets. By examining the relationship between these ratios and firm performance, this study aims to provide insights into the financial health of companies and the factors that contribute to their success.

In this study, we aim to analyze the effects of corporate governance by utilizing the following equation:

$$\text{CH}_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{PROM}_{it} + \beta_2 \text{INSTI}_{it} + \beta_3 \text{SIZE}_{it} + \beta_4 \text{LEV}_{it} + \beta_5 \text{C_FLOW}_{it} + U_i + V_t + \epsilon_{i,t} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Results& Discussion

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of India

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	CH	PROM O	INSTI	Size	Leve	C-FLOW
CH	20810	0.0259	1.8647	1					
PROM O	20810	0.5180	0.2881	0.1115	1.0000				

INSTI	2081 0	0.423 9	0.1610	- 0.0311 *	- 0.3309 *	1.0000			
Size	2081 0	8.388 6	2.2273	- 0.0916 *	0.0602 *	- 0.0510 *	1.0000		
Leve	2081 0	0.353 4	2.0662	- 0.0155 *	0.0825 *	0.0359 *	- 0.0557 *	1.0000	
C- FLOW	2081 0	0.076 5	0.1845	- 0.0256 *	0.1026 *	0.0239 *	- 0.0192 *	0.0213 *	1

Note: This study presents a table containing the descriptive statistics and correlation matrix of the primary variables utilized in the research. The descriptive statistics of the variables were computed and reported in terms of the mean and standard deviation. * The observed result indicates statistical significance at a significance level of 1%.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix of China

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	CH	PROM O	INSTI	Size	Leve	C- FLOW
CH	701 2	0.1467	0.1372	1.0000					
PROMO	701 2	0.8906	0.2236	0.0282*	1.0000				
INSTI	701 2	0.6698	0.4058	-0.0107	-0.0049	1.0000			
Size	701 2	8.6588	1.7647	- 0.1679*	0.0164	- 0.0200	1.0000		
Leve	701 2	0.0910	0.1211	- 0.2867*	-0.0022	0.0235	0.3073 *	1.000 0	

C- FLOW	701 2	- 0.1583	10.8606	-0.0288	-0.0053	- 0.0111	0.1039 *	0.013 2	1.0000
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Note: This Table reports the descriptive statistics and correlation matrix of the main variables used in the study.

For each variable, we report the mean and standard deviation. * Denotes significance at 1% level. The descriptive statistics show that promoter holdings account for 51.80 percent in India and 89.9 percent in China, implying that promoter ownership is high in China due to the state-owned structure. On average institutional ownership account for only 42.2 percent of ownership in India and 66.6 percent in China. The correlation matrix shows promoter ownership positively affects cash holdings in India and China.

Table 3: Impact of Corporate Governance on Cash Holdings

	India	China
PROMO	0.0002***	0.0169**
	(8.85)	(1.98)
INSTI	0.0020	0.0044
	(0.67)	(0.96)
Size	0.0002	-0.0008
	(0.83)	(-0.71)
Leve	-0.0010**	-0.3348***
	(-2.36)	(-20.31)
C-FLOW	-0.0355***	0.0001
	(-5.78)	(0.54)
Constant	0.0091***	0.1619***
	(3.25)	(12.45)
R-Squared	0.55	0.60
Observations	20380	7012
Year Effect	YES	YES
Industry Effect	YES	YES

Note: This table reports the impact of corporate governance on cash holdings. Detailed variable definitions are provided in Appendix "II." All regressions control for industry and year-fixed effects. T-statistics are in brackets. ***, **, * denote significance at the 1%, 5% and 10% significance level, respectively.

Table 3 This study investigates the impact of corporate governance mechanisms, specifically promoter and institutional ownership, on the valuation of firms. The study reveals a positive and statistically significant association between promoter ownership and cash reserves in India and China. The present study investigates the impact of institutional ownership on corporate governance in India and China. The findings reveal that institutional ownership has a positive effect on corporate governance. However, the effect is statistically insignificant, indicating that corporate governance in these countries is weak. According to research findings, promoters tend to have a higher cash reserve and enjoy greater autonomy in deciding whether or not to distribute dividends to external investors. The study examines the impact of institutional dividends on the cash-holding decisions of firms and how it affects their power to influence such decisions. It is observed that institutional dividend varies, and this variation significantly affects the ability of these firms to influence their cash-holding decisions.

Conclusion

This study examines corporate governance systems' impact on cash holdings. The present study highlights the significance of corporate governance practices in determining a firm's financial resources. It is suggested that effective corporate governance procedures play a crucial role in determining a company's cash reserves. This study examines the impact of various components of the corporate governance framework on a firm's cash reserves. Specifically, the study delves into the ownership structure, promoters, and institutional ownership to assess their influence on the company's cash holdings. Using benchmarks is crucial for companies to determine their optimal cash reserves. Therefore, firms should incorporate these benchmarks into their financial management strategies. The study's results suggest a positive correlation between elevated promoter ownership and increased cash reserves in publicly traded firms. The observed phenomenon can be attributed to the potential increase in the prevalence of asymmetric information.

The present study identified time constraints and restricted access to data as the two most significant obstacles encountered during the research process. As the study duration is prolonged, an increase in the sample size leads to enhanced outcomes. Furthermore, the study excludes

companies that fail to provide consistent yearly reports and statistics on various critical factors, including CEO duality and board of directors. However, these entities may be incorporated into the investigation through primary data. Corporate governance's potential impact on financial service providers' cash reserves could be a good subject for scholarly inquiry.

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